

The Enchanting Kingfisher: Stories of Wisdom and Reflection

 Minh-Phuong Thi Duong

Faculty of Social Sciences and Humanities

Ton Duc Thang University, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2487-9905>

September 3, 2023

[BOOK REVIEW]

**Editorial Note: This column reprints the Book Review on Amazon.com.au with permission from Dr. Phuong Duong, Ton Duc Thang University. It has been slightly edited for a house-style presentation.*

When I first laid eyes on this book, I was immediately captivated by the cover photo featuring the enchanting Kingfisher, who also to be the central character throughout the entire [series of short stories](#) [1].

As I delved into each story, my fascination only grew, and I found myself completely engrossed in the world of this remarkable character. The author's writing, filled with intelligence, humor, and wit, added an extra layer of intrigue to the tales.

Through Kingfisher's life journey and interactions with other characters, these stories beautifully impart profound life lessons. I deeply appreciate how the author encourages readers to scrutinize the characters' actions in the stories, fostering the growth of critical thinking skills. Take, for instance, the character Guru Bird, who is held in high esteem by the villagers for his wisdom and guidance. However, as the story unfolds, it becomes apparent that Guru Bird's expertise may be confined to offering advice and ideas rather than

showcasing practical skills or actions. This narrative evokes a sense of skepticism and underscores the truth that actions often convey more than words.

What follows is a series of other stories about invaluable lessons in cultural awareness and ethics, encompassing themes such as deception, arrogance, greed, carelessness, and the consequences of receiving something without effort.

Illustration. Review on Amazon Australia: https://www.amazon.com.au/gp/customer-reviews/R3TUF78IVCRI5D/ref=cm_cr_srp_d_rvw_ttl?ie=UTF8&ASIN=B0BG2NNHY6 [1]

I can imagine that as readers hold this book in their hands, older individuals will feel a deep sense of empathy, drawing from their own life experiences and the profound lessons within. At the same time, the younger generation will develop a wider perspective and a deeper grasp of universal human values, contributing to their personal growth.

I can't wait for the author's next books with great excitement.

References

[1] Vuong QH. (2022). *Wild Wise Weird*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/BOBG2NNHY6>

©2024 AISDL - Science Portal for the [SM3D Knowledge Management Theory](#)